

tropical American rice-growing areas is susceptible to the BSBR pathogen (see table). Previous reports limited the host range to the Gramineae; however, our results show that species from other families within the Monocotyledoneae may be hosts as well. The bacterium

was weakly pathogenic on a few dicots. Roots of most inoculated plants harbored the pathogen, usually in large amounts.

How rapid, or by what means plant-to-plant transmission may occur in the field is unclear and the extent to which

fields planted with clean seed may be recontaminated is unknown. Weeds may harbor the pathogen and the high recovery rate of the pathogen from roots suggests that plant debris in the soil also may serve as an inoculum source or survival site. $\mathcal{J}$

Weeds as alternate hosts of *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk in Cuba

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Many graminicolous weeds of ricefields have been reported to host *Thanatephorus cucumeris*. The resistance to *T. cucumeris* of some weeds was investigated under controlled and field conditions. Plants were inoculated under the leaf sheath with a 3-mm-diameter disk of PDA-grown culture of the fungus and covered with PVC bands to avoid desiccation.

Table 1. Reactions of weeds inoculated with *T. cucumeris* under controlled condition. RRS, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba.

Weed	Infestation (%)	Length of lesions (mm)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	50	37.1
<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>	30	33.2
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	10	20.0
<i>E. colona</i>	10	20.0
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	10	3.5

Under controlled conditions, *Echinochloa crus-galli* and *Leptochloa fascicularis* were most susceptible and *Cynodon dactylon* most resistant (Table 1). In the field, *E. crus-galli* was very susceptible and *C. dactylon* and

Table 2. Reaction of weeds inoculated with *T. cucumeris* in the field. RRS, Sancti Spiritus, Cuba.

Weed	Infestation (%)	Length of lesions (mm)
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	100	80.3
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	100	40.3
<i>Leptochloa fascicularis</i>	100	25.0
<i>E. colona</i>	100	20.5
<i>Oryza latifolia</i>	100	20.0
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	100	10.4
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i>	70	10.1
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	50	9.2
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	40	18.0

Eleusine indica resistant (Table 2). Inoculations in the field were more effective than in controlled conditions.

Evaluation of decamethrin concentrations for tungro disease and vector control

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Different concentrations of decamethrin were evaluated under field conditions in a randomized block design. Taichung Native 1 (TN1) (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant) were planted in 3- $\times$ 3-m plots. Decamethrin and cypermethrin were sprayed at 10-d intervals from 15 d after transplanting (DT) to 45 DT.

Carbofuran was broadcast at 15-d intervals from 15 DT to 45 DT. Three tungro-infected plants of cultivar Jaya were introduced into each plot just before the first spraying. The vector population was recorded at 30 and 42 DT and disease incidence at 49 DT. In TN1, disease incidence was low in

Efficacy of decamethrin concentrations on tungro disease incidence and vector density in TN1 and Ratna.^a CRRI, Orissa, India.

Insecticide	Dose (g ai/ha)	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers ^b (no./20 hills)			
		TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1		Ratna	
						Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
Decamethrin	200	3 a	2 a	3.3 a	4.7 a	3	0	1	0
Decamethrin	100	4 a	2 a	3.1 a	4.3 ab	5	2	1	0
Decamethrin	50	5 ab	4 b	2.6 b	4.0 bc	5	3	5	1
Decamethrin	25	6 b	5 bc	2.4 b	3.8 bcd	7	4	6	1
Decamethrin	12	10 c	5 bc	2.4 b	3.4 d	8	4	8	2
Decamethrin	6	81 e	5 bc	0.7 b	3.4 d	16	13	7	4
Cypermethrin	100	6 b	2 a	2.6 b	3.6 cd	3	2	2	1
Carbofuran	2 kg	19 d	12 d	1.4 c	3.5 cd	9	22	13	34
Control	-	100 f	44 e	0.2 e	2.4 e	51	152	43	104

^aSeparation of means in each column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bAv values of 30 and 42 DT.

plots treated with decamethrin at higher than 12 g ai/ha (see table). In Ratna, disease incidence was almost negligible at all concentrations. Cypermethrin equaled carbofuran and 6, 12, 25 g ai/ha decamethrin. Yields in the control were

significantly less than in insecticide-treated plots. The trends in vector population (adults and nymphs) in both cultivars was similar to that of disease incidence.

The conclusion is that 12 g ai/ha of

decamethrin in susceptible TN1 and 6 g ai/ha in tolerant Ratna seem to be the lowest possible doses to reduce disease incidence. *J*

Evaluation of some new synthetic pyrethroids for tungro (RTV) disease and vector control

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Some new synthetic pyrethroids were evaluated against RTV in the field.

Cypermethrin, decamethrin, and carbofuran were included as checks.

Synthetic pyrethroids were sprayed at 10-d intervals from 15 d after transplanting (DT) and to 45 DT. Carbofuran was broadcast at 15-d intervals. Test cultivars were TN1 (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant). Design was a randomized block in 3- $\times$ 3-m plots with 3 replications for each cultivar. RTV source was artificially induced. Leafhopper population was

recorded at 30 DT, disease incidence at 51 DT, and grain yield at harvest.

Decamethrin + buprofezin (200 g ai/ha), tralomethrin (20 g ai/ha), cypermethrin (50 g ai/ha), and decamethrin (12 g ai/ha) were equally effective in reducing RTV incidence and vector leafhopper populations in cultivar TN1 (see table). In cultivar Ratna, carbofuran and S-423 (1000 g ai/ha) also were effective in reducing RTV incidence and leafhopper population. *J*

Effect of some new synthetic pyrethroids on RTV and vector populations in TN1 and Ratna.^a CRRI, India.

Insecticide	Concentration (g ai/ha)	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers/20 hills at 30 DT			
		TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1		Ratna	
						Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
Decamethrin + buprofezin (S-534)	100	42 b	8 bc	0.8 c	3.5 cde	15 ab	11 bc	12 bcd	4 ab
	200	20 a	6 ab	1.4 a	4.3 ab	9 a	7 abc	9 abcd	2 a
Tralomethrin (S-528)	10	44 b	10 c	0.8 c	3.7 bcd	19 bc	12 bc	6 abc	7 b
	20	22 a	4 a	1.4 a	4.2 abc	10 a	3 a	5 ab	2 a
S-399	125	100 c	39 f	0.2 e	2.6 f	42 e	91 f	30 g	41 e
	250	96 c	24 e	0.2 e	2.9 ef	42 e	71 ef	19 efg	27 d
S-423	500	97 c	15 d	0.2 e	3.3 def	34 de	23 d	20 fg	13 c
	1000	57 b	8 bc	0.4 d	4.1 abc	30 cde	14 cd	16 def	6 ab
Cypermethrin	50	21 a	4 a	1.5 a	4.3 ab	12 ab	5 ab	3 a	3 ab
Decamethrin	12	20 a	5 a	1.5 a	4.3 ab	12 ab	7 abc	6 abc	3 ab
Carbofuran	2 kg	47 b	11 cd	1.3 b	4.7 a	25 cd	55 e	14 cdef	14 c
Control	-	100 c	42 f	0.2 e	2.9 ef	49 e	120 g	29 g	59 f

^aValues followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Relation between rice sheath blight (ShB) and yield

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A generalized relationship between ShB level and yield loss has not been

established across rice-growing environments, mainly because of differences in disease evaluation methods, cultivars used, and disease pressures encountered.

To assess the disease more efficiently, data sets from national reports were analyzed. All data on disease measurement were transformed to

relative lesion height (RLH) (ratio of vertical lesion height of the uppermost leaf or sheath lesion to plant height). Disease severities in scales or range were transformed to mid-RLH values.

Despite divergent environments and different cultivars used, a positive and highly significant linear relationship between RLH of ShB and yield